

“ENTITY RESOLUTION: META-BLOCKING AND KLSH”

Author: Sergio Solorzano Gimenez
Independent Researcher

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ABSTRACT We perform an exploration to solve an entity resolution problem based on blocking rules and a K-Means clustering algorithm. The proposed approach has three sequential stages. Firstly, the generation of a hierarchical graph for records in blocks, followed by the generation of a record relationship graph with components; we further enhance the pipeline by tuning each component’s feature weights via Bayesian optimization prior to k-means clustering enabling separation of piano models despite omitting their explicit name labels; finally, we cluster the records for each component using a K-Means algorithm. We conclude the results are encouraging and we identify multiple further research opportunities to improve our results.

INDEX TERMS algorithms, blocking, clustering, cluster, deduplication, entity resolution, graph, klsh, k-means, linkage, machine learning, meta-blocking, tabular data

I. INTRODUCTION

Our approach aims at solving an entity resolution problem based on blocking rules and a K-Means clustering algorithm.

The proposed approach has three sequential stages. Firstly, the generation of a hierarchical graph for records in blocks, followed by the generation of a record relationship graph with components; finally, we cluster the records for each component using a K-Means algorithm.

Hierarchical graph: We build a hierarchical directed graph where each level corresponds to blocks generated from a blocking rule/s.

Each block in a graph level groups co-occurring records in blocks based on a rule. Hierarchical rules applied to blocks yield children blocks at deeper graph levels.

Record Relationship graph: Two records in a block is referred as that they co-occur and this relationship is represented as an edge between these two records. We graph co-occurrence and edges in a record relationship graph where we refer to records as nodes.

In this record relationship graph, components are formed when a group of nodes are all connected to each other, either directly, or indirectly through other nodes.

We increase the count of a node edge, referred to as an edge weight, for each co-occurrence. This weight metric signals the strength of a relationship between records.

We prune components according to a threshold number of edge count between nodes.

The generation of clustering components reduces all dataset record comparisons which is an $O(n^2)$ to $O(n)$ thus reducing the computational requirements for downstream processing since we would only be comparing records within components; the approach helps us present a reasonable scalable solution.

Assuming 1000 records, from $n*(n-1)/2 = 1000*999/2 = 499,500$ comparisons without blocking to:

assuming 100 components evenly split with 10 records each, $10*9/2=45$ comparisons per component $45 * 100$ components = 4500

== That’s over 110x reduction in comparisons ==

KLSH: This work builds upon the methodology proposed by Steorts, Rebecca C., Anshumali Shrivastava “Probabilistic Blocking with An Application to the Syrian

Conflict” [1]. Component records are broken down into clusters applying a K-Means algorithm, the approach of which is referred herein from existing research [1] as KLSH.

K-means is helpful in that it can place records that are similar in the same bucket or cluster but apart from those that are different; the approach treats each cluster as a bucket mimicking LSH though it doesn’t use hashing.

We apply and optimize record feature weights via Bayesian Optimization and transform these features which are inputs into K-means to calculate the square Euclidean distances to centroids and cluster records.

We conclude the results are encouraging and we identify multiple further research opportunities to improve our results.

The code for this project is available in the Github repo¹ [2]. The project is an experimental prototype for research and does not address full error handling or production standards, and it’s rather a setup for quick prototyping.

II. DATASET

We generate an imaginary dataset [3] by creating different brands of pianos and selecting features that require normalization with different methods, including numeric, dates and ordinal and *Boolean* categorical.

The piano model names are purposefully omitted in the dataset to test record linkage within brands for different models without the model’s name feature.

Typos for the features of the dataset have been added to challenge the approach.

We then compare the resulting entity component clusters to the expected results when we created the dataset.

The dataset is small and holds twenty records and it is sufficient for an initial indication of the potential of this approach.

III. METHODOLOGY

We create a dataset where record features have multiple typos and differences. This helps us assess the robustness of the clustering approach.

A. GROUND TRUTH RESULTS

We classify ground truth for records in each component. Our complete labelled piano dataset contains 3 brands (Apollo, August Förster, Baldwin) and 2 unclassified records that may therefore be a different brand. Moreover, the dataset contains 4 models identified for each brand (2 models of Apollo, 1 August Förster, 1 Baldwin), and the 2 unclassified models mentioned above.

Viewed in a graph, we find the following subsets of a graph, referred herein as components:

1) COMPONENT 0

See dataset rows related to the brand name Apollo. This component hosts records of 2 models of the same brand (Apollo). We note that we deem as ground truth record 3 an Apollo model that contains above average typos.

A third model, coined herein as a singleton, is also grouped within this component (record 5). By singleton we mean a graph node without any edges so that its features do not closely match those of any other record from the same brand. Thus, this record may be a different brand and model.

```
ground_truth_pairs_component_0 = [(0, 1), (0, 2), (0, 3),
(0, 4), (1, 2), (1, 3), (1, 4), (2, 3), (2, 4), (3, 4), (6, 7), (6, 8),
(6, 9), (7, 8), (7, 9), (8, 9)]
singleton = [5]
```

2) COMPONENT 1

See dataset rows related to brand name August Förster. This component hosts records of 1 model of the same brand (August Förster).

A second model represented as a singleton is also grouped within this component (record 14). Thus, this record may be a different brand and model.

```
ground_truth_pairs_component_1 = [(10, 11), (10, 12),
(10, 13), (10, 15), (11, 12), (11, 13), (11, 15), (12, 13), (12,
15), (13, 15)]
singleton = [14]
```

3) COMPONENT 2

See dataset rows related to the brand name Baldwin. All records in this component are grouped together for the same brand and model.

```
ground_truth_pairs_component_2 = [(16, 17), (16, 18),
(16, 19), (16, 20), (17, 18), (17, 19), (17, 20), (18, 19), (18,
20), (19, 20)]
singleton = [ ]
```

IV. METHODOLOGY STEPS

A. STEP 1 - META-BLOCKING AND GRAPHS

1) BLOCK GENERATION

We create blocks with a lenient phonetic rule applied to the dataset’s piano model names. Records are clustered in the blocks where they match any of the rules - the first char, first two char, the first three char, last three char or has all consonants.

Rules are easily extendable and can be arranged to generate blocks in a hierarchical or flat order. For example, we can block feature *name* at the first graph hierarchical level for the rule *phonetic_combination* which generates flat blocks for

¹https://github.com/sergiosolorzano/entity_resolution/tree/main/block_k_lsh

multiple sub-rules (“*first_char*”, “*first_two_char*”, “*first_three_char*”, “*last_three_char*”, “*consonants*”), and generate the second level graph blocks from the first for feature *date* for a temporal *sliding_window* rule.

Blocking rules can easily be extended to experiment with new business rules, adopt new ones or factor in edge cases:

```
{
  "rules": {
    "phonetic_combination": {
      "type": "text",
      "params": {
        "algorithms": [
          "first_char", "first_two_char", "first_three_char", "last_three_char", "consonants"
        ]
      },
      "default": false,
      "description": "multi-method name blocking"
    },
    "sliding_window": {
      "type": "temporal",
      "params": {"window_days": 7},
      "default": false,
      "description": "7-day sliding window blocks"
    }
  }
}
```

```
def _phonetic_combination(self, feature_series: pd.Series, method_params:dict, feature_name:str) -> pd.Series:
    def encode_combo(x):
        key_list = []
        if "first_char" in method_params["algorithms"]:
            key_list.append(str(x).lower()[0:1])
        if "first_two_char" in method_params["algorithms"]:
            key_list.append(str(x).lower()[0:2])
        if "first_three_char" in method_params["algorithms"]:
            key_list.append(str(x).lower()[0:3])
        if "last_three_char" in method_params["algorithms"]:
            key_list.append(str(x).lower()[-3:])
        if "consonants" in method_params["algorithms"]:
            key_list.append(''.join([c for c in str(x).lower() if c.isalpha() and c not in 'aeiou']))
        return key_list
    return feature_series.apply(encode_combo)
```

This is an example of a block that is created from the first three letters of a brand name:

```
Block Key initial_block-name_phonetic_combination:ap
Block Hierarchy Level: 1
Block Feature: name
Block Parent Key: initial_block
Block Key: initial_block-name_phonetic_combination:ap
Leaf Key: phonetic_combination:ap
Block Rule: phonetic_combination
Block Record Indices: [0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]
```

This tree graph shows the blocks in a graph where each record lands:

We will not use this graph in this experiment, but as an example, this is how a two-level graph with a second rule may

look like. Due to the multiple blocks involved, these are visually a bit mushed together in the snapshot:

2) GRAPH COMPONENTS

Two records in a block (e.g. as per a blocking rule, they both have the first three letters in the name) is referred as that they co-occur. If records match on multiple rules they'll co-occur on multiple blocks. Therefore, records can have multiple connections to other records as they co-occur in multiple blocks.

We represent record blocking relationships in a second graph we coin record relationship graph. Here each record is a node and each co-occurrence between records represents an edge between the records. In this record relationship graph, components are formed when a group of nodes are all connected to each other, either directly, or indirectly through other nodes.

We track block provenance so that each time two records co-occur in the same block, their edge weight increases by 1. This weight metric signals the strength of a relationship between records. Records whose edge weight is above a certain threshold form a graph component.

Similarly, experimenting with blocking rules can help avoid co-occurrence on different brand names (e.g. Apollo and Baldwin), so that each name creates their own graph component. The numbers on the edge shown below tells us how many times records co-occur in the graph.

Pre-pruning Provenance Components Graph

3) PRUNED COMPONENTS

We can assume that two records that co-occur in exactly one block throughout the graph is not sufficient to signal that they are closely related and belong to the same component. In this project, we set the number of required edges to be ≥ 2 for records to be part of the same component.

The resulting components from re-arranging nodes according to the number of node edge connections or weights produces a component for all Apollo brand records and its variations. Two further components are generated for piano models of the brands August Forster and Baldwin.

At this point however, the certainty that these records belong to a brand or are instances of the same model is limited to discrete blocking rules and an edge count threshold. An algorithmic approach that leverages all record features will enable us to cluster records with some desired level of certainty. Fortunately, also at this point the placement of records in components reduces the comparison space from $O(n^2)$ to $O(n)$, meaning a more limited number of record pairs that we need to evaluate whilst maintaining a high recall to capture all true matches and precision to avoid false matches; domain input can help steer the algorithm to target either recall or precision.

Additional rules can be added to block further, but its discrete approach risks overfitting. Here, there may be scope for further research that may yield interesting results by selecting blocking rules, their hierarchical order and alter rule values (e.g. number of bins, sampling such as *np.linspace*, *np.logspace*, etc) with Bayesian optimization.

B. STEP 2 – K-MEANS LOCALITY SENSITIVE HASHING (KLSH)

Recap: We initially broke out records into components by taking a blocking approach that operates in discrete space and by generating sparse blocks. We do not block further at the risk of overfitting.

Instead, for each component, we generate dense clusters using the k-means algorithm which operates on transformed numerical features in continuous space. This approach enables us to map similar items to the same bucket based on minimizing the distance to initially randomly initialized cluster centroids:

1) FEATURE TRANSFORMATION

We create a multi-dimensional feature representation by transforming each feature into numerical vectors and constructing a single feature array:

- Numeric (features *tension*, *resonance*, *amount_sold*): we generate 1d scaled feature values by fitting these to a standard scaler
- Boolean nominal category (feature *tension_adj*): we generated 2d embeddings of its value by encoding it to a point on the unit quarter circle: $0 \rightarrow (1.0, 0.0)$ and $1 \rightarrow (0.0, 1.0)$
- Ordinal category (features *quality*): we generated 2d continuous embeddings of its values by encoding these to a point on a quarter circle where the angle increases linearly from 0 to $\pi/2$ as the ordinal value increases. We note we did not test one hot encoding as we were curious to test the results from this approach.
- Dates (*longevity*): we encode temporal information into a continuous numerical feature by mapping the fraction of time passed from 1/1/2015 to an angle in the quarter-circle. This helps us retain a distance measure for each record feature's value and it's more adaptable to scale it by a feature weight.

2) WEIGHT RELATIVE IMPORTANCE OF DIFFERENT FEATURES

We manually weight each resulting transformed feature vector to better fit the KLSH clustering results to our dataset's ground truth. At a later stage in our project, these weights are optimized with Bayesian optimization.

3) K-MEANS FITTING

We cluster records using a k-means algorithm with an adjustable k parameter.

The algorithm iteratively assigns each record in a component to its nearest centroid based on Euclidean distance, recalculates the centroids using the means of all its assigned records and repeat this until we reach converge. This approach helps us group similar records to a cluster where we minimize the sum of squared distances between records and the centroid. Finally, we select the k cluster result output from the algorithm by considering F1, silhouette scores and the elbow method results.

This approach results in a separation of piano models within components and therefore piano brands.

The above-mentioned method helps us group the Apollo records into the two separate entities.

4) K-MEANS CLUSTERING

(1) Component Zero

We transform numeric data to be used by K-means for the first component with record indices {0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9}.

We run K-means for K=10 clusters:

== Final Clusters: ==

k=1: {0: [0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]}
 k=2: {0: [3], 1: [0, 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]}
 k=3: {0: [3], 1: [5, 6, 7, 8, 9], 2: [0, 1, 2, 4]}
 k=4: {0: [3], 1: [6, 7, 8, 9], 2: [0, 1, 2, 4], 3: [5]}
 k=5: {0: [3], 1: [6, 7, 8, 9], 2: [0, 1, 2], 3: [5], 4: [4]}
 k=6: {0: [3], 1: [6, 7, 8, 9], 2: [0, 2], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [1]}
 k=7: {0: [3], 1: [6, 7, 9], 2: [0, 2], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [1], 6: [8]}
 k=8: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [0, 2], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [1], 6: [8], 7: [6, 9]}
 k=9: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [0], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [1], 6: [8], 7: [6, 9], 8: [2]}
 k=10: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [0], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [1], 6: [8], 7: [9], 8: [2], 9: [6]}

A visual interpretation of the Elbow method suggests K=4; the KneeLocator library suggests K=1 or 4 (depending on omitting curve and direction).

Sklearn's Silhouette method suggests K=4.

Best F-1 suggests K=4.

K	F1	Precision	Recall
1	0.524590	0.355556	1.0000
2	0.461538	0.333333	0.7500
3	0.750000	0.750000	0.7500
4	0.857143	1.000000	0.7500
5	0.720000	1.000000	0.5625
6	0.608696	1.000000	0.4375
7	0.400000	1.000000	0.2500

K	F1	Precision	Recall
8	0.222222	1.000000	0.1250
9	0.117647	1.000000	0.0625
10	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000

Thus, we choose the highest F-1 K-Means best result, k=4; the algorithm incorrectly classifies record 3 as a singleton:

k=4: {0: [3], 1: [6, 7, 8, 9], 2: [0, 1, 2, 4], 3: [5]}

We run the equivalent unsupervised K-Means predictions for Component 1 and 2 with the following results:

(2) Component One

== Final Clusters: ==

k=1: {0: [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]}
 k=2: {0: [11, 12, 14], 1: [10, 13, 15]}
 k=3: {0: [12], 1: [15], 2: [10, 11, 13, 14]}
 k=4: {0: [12], 1: [15], 2: [10, 11, 13], 3: [14]}
 k=5: {0: [12], 1: [15], 2: [10, 13], 3: [14], 4: [11]}
 k=6: {0: [12], 1: [15], 2: [10], 3: [14], 4: [11], 5: [13]}
 Singletons: []

K	F1	Precision	Recall
1	0.800000	0.666667	1.0000
2	0.500000	0.666667	0.4000
3	0.375000	0.500000	0.3000
4	0.461538	1.000000	0.3000
5	0.181818	1.000000	0.1000
6	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000

Elbow K is hard to tell, suggested [KneeLocator](#) K=1 or 4.

Sklearn's [Silhouette](#) method suggests $K=4$.

Best F-1 suggestion $K=1$.

We choose the highest F-1 at $K=1$ as a possible best solution, which incorrectly classifies record 14.

$k=1$: {0: [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]}

(3) Component Two

== Final Clusters: ==

$k=1$: {0: [16, 17, 18, 19, 20]}

$k=2$: {0: [17], 1: [16, 18, 19, 20]}

$k=3$: {0: [17], 1: [20], 2: [16, 18, 19]}

$k=4$: {0: [17], 1: [20], 2: [16, 18], 3: [19]}

$k=5$: {0: [17], 1: [20], 2: [16], 3: [19], 4: [18]}

Singletons: []

K	F1	Precision	Recall
1	1.000000	1.000000	1.0000
2	0.750000	1.000000	0.6000
3	0.461538	1.000000	0.3000
4	0.181818	1.000000	0.1000
5	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000
5	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000

Elbow K suggested by KneeLocator $K=1$ or 4; visually $k=4$.

Sklearn's Silhouette method suggests $K=4$.

Best F-1 suggestion $K=1$.

We choose the highest F-1 at $K=1$ as a possible best solution, which correctly classifies all records.

We conclude

Component 0: Incorrectly classifies record 3 as a singleton.

Component 1: Incorrectly groups record 14.

Component 2: Correctly groups all records when choosing best F-1

B. STEP 3 - K-MEANS CLUSTERING: WEIGHTING TRANSFORMED FEATURE DATA

We will now seek to improve classification.

So far, we have applied a uniform weight to all numeric features. Next, we explore custom weights for each feature using supervised Bayesian Optimization across all K over 100 calls, with objective function targeting the average of all components' results $F1=1$.

Further research is warranted to explore the design of an objective function targeting desired outcome such as $F1=Precision=Recall=1$ and biasing the optimization towards the preferred domain requirements.

In the scenario we have run, Bayesian plateaus and provides multiple - 56 - best weights for the highest best results. Thus, we average these.

We also note that a weight observed multiple times at zero can be a hint that a particular feature is not adding much to model training and perhaps can be dropped. In such case and in this project, we do not remove a feature.

The best Bayesian optimization results have the following feature weights and metrics:

Average F1 0.9523

Average Precision 1

Average Recall 0.9166

Average Bayesian Feature Weights = [0.32922948, 0.36130566, 0.20008195, 0.82066852, 0.44855293, 0.62657605, 0.36378109, 0.4405338, 0.2413675]

We re-run KLSH with these weights and for each Component we select the cluster results for the earliest highest F-1 in the dataframe. Therefore, we judge the success of the clustering algorithm result based on F-1 which does not require the implementation of an automated elbow method result interpretation and decision process.

1) COMPONENT 0: INCORRECT AT $K=4$

Best silhouette $K=2$; Elbow Knee $K=1$ or 3, Visual Elbow $k=3$ or 4; $F1=4$

$k=5$: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [0, 1, 2, 4], 3: [5], 4: [6, 8, 9]}

$k=6$: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [0, 2], 3: [5], 4: [6, 8, 9], 5: [1, 4]}

$k=7$: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [0, 2], 3: [5], 4: [6, 8, 9], 5: [1], 6: [4]}

$k=8$: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [0, 2], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [6, 9], 6: [1], 7: [8]}

$k=9$: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [2], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [6, 9], 6: [1], 7: [8], 8: [0]}

$k=10$: {0: [3], 1: [7], 2: [2], 3: [5], 4: [4], 5: [6], 6: [1], 7: [8], 8: [0], 9: [9]}

K	F1	Precision	Recall
1	0.524590	0.355556	1.0000
2	0.461538	0.333333	0.7500
3	0.750000	0.750000	0.7500
4	0.857143	1.000000	0.7500
5	0.720000	1.000000	0.5625
6	0.476190	1.000000	0.3125
7	0.400000	1.000000	0.2500
8	0.222222	1.000000	0.1250
9	0.117647	1.000000	0.0625
10	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000

2) COMPONENT 1: CORRECT AT K=2

Best silhouette K = 2; Elbow Knee K = 1 or 2, Visual Elbow k=2; F1=2

== Final Clusters: ==

- k=1: {0: [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]}
- k=2: {0: [10, 11, 12, 13, 15], 1: [14]}
- k=3: {0: [11, 12], 1: [14], 2: [10, 13, 15]}
- k=4: {0: [11, 12], 1: [14], 2: [10, 13], 3: [15]}
- k=5: {0: [12], 1: [14], 2: [10, 13], 3: [15], 4: [11]}
- k=6: {0: [12], 1: [14], 2: [10], 3: [15], 4: [11], 5: [13]}

K	F1	Precision	Recall
1	0.800000	0.666667	1.0
2	1.000000	1.000000	1.0
3	0.571429	1.000000	0.4
4	0.333333	1.000000	0.2
5	0.181818	1.000000	0.1

K	F1	Precision	Recall
6	0.000000	0.000000	0.0

3) COMPONENT 2: CORRECT AT K=1

Best silhouette K = 2; Elbow Knee K = 1 or 2, Visual Elbow k=2; F1=1

== Final Clusters: ==

- k=1: {0: [16, 17, 18, 19, 20]}
- k=2: {0: [17], 1: [16, 18, 19, 20]}
- k=3: {0: [17], 1: [16, 19, 20], 2: [18]}
- k=4: {0: [17], 1: [16, 20], 2: [18], 3: [19]}
- k=5: {0: [17], 1: [20], 2: [18], 3: [19], 4: [16]}

K	F1	Precision	Recall
1	1.000000	1.0	1.0
2	0.750000	1.0	0.6
3	0.461538	1.0	0.3
4	0.181818	1.0	0.1
5	0.000000	0.0	0.0

We conclude:

The silhouette score is significantly more consistent for these runs though not necessarily more accurate.

Component 0 incorrectly classifies record 3. The remaining records are correctly grouped. It is fair to say record 3's ground truth may have also been a singleton with the assumptions we made and perhaps we were too extreme.

Component 1 Correctly classifies groups and singleton.

Component 2: correctly classifies all records in the same group.

C. STEP 4 - COSINE SIMILARITY OVERLAY TO KLSH RESULTS

Further research may benefit this analysis by normalizing the transformed features as input to the K-Means algorithm and thereby remove the influence of magnitude. A more manually laborious but perhaps insightful approach may be by filtering out input records to the K-Means algorithm based on cosine similarity to focus on the angle between

vectors and remove the influence of magnitude, unlike the K-Means Euclidean distance.

As shown on the heat map below which shows the cosine similarity for records in component 0, we may have been too extreme adding typos to the dataset features for record 3 and it may deserve to be an entity by itself and indeed unrelated to records 0,1,2,4.

D. RESULTS

We conclude that post feature weight optimization, the training set exhibits the following performance metrics:

Component	F1	Precision	Recall
0	0.857143	1.000000	0.750000
1	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
2	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
Average	0.952381	1.000000	0.916667

Generalization of these results with a larger training dataset and an evaluation dataset may surface considerations not addressed and yield better results.

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The resulting F-1/Precision/Recall=0.952/1.00/0.916 is a good start and domain input on blocking rules, feature engineering experimentation and transformations can greatly increase these results.

A blocking graph approach helps us scale this solution for larger datasets by reducing all record comparisons which is an $O(n)$ to $O(n)$. Smaller datasets may benefit from skipping blocking all together and creating embeddings for those features, e.g. in the case of this publication, a phonetic embedding for record names.

The blocking rules approach can be easily expanded and capture nuances specific to the domain with a deeper graph.

The pre-processing techniques applied to a dataset, distance metric and clustering algorithm can have a significant impact on the final clustering results. In this project, we found that optimizing feature weights helped us correctly classify the records in one of the two incorrectly classified components. In addition, further distance conditions in pair selection may also help capture outliers and new entities. This provides an interesting opportunity to create ensembles and diversify the way we capture nuances in the dataset.

Blocking rule refinement and the optimization of the order as to how these are applied can generate more accurate component composition results and help in finding singletons pre-KLSH clustering. Elbow and silhouette unsupervised k-determination is difficult. For instance, the K determined by the KneeLocator library requires the user to run the algorithm having previously established the type of curve (convex, concave) and its slope. An automated solution or computer vision solution can help us determine the value for these parameters, but we find that the user's visual comparison of these metrics and F-1 helps reach a more robust k-determination.

We often find that a production pipeline requires the program to determine K without user intervention. There may be scope for further research to achieve this by training a classifier such as XGBoost, and using an X-training_dataset composed of the record features, Elbow KneeLocator K result, silhouette score K result, and a desired F-1/Precision/Recall target; the Y-training_dataset the ground truth K.

The resulting Bayesian optimized weights gives us some insight into the average importance placed by the model across features, components and clusters. We observe resonance and longevity_sin drive a great deal of the result in this analysis whilst the tension feature does not. Domain knowledge may bias these results or justify its meaning.

Feature	Weight
tension_adj_cos	0.32922948
tension_adj_sin	0.36130566
tension	0.20008195
resonance	0.82066852
longevity_cos	0.44855293
longevity_sin	0.62657605
quality_cos	0.36378109
quality_sin	0.44053380

Feature	Weight
amt_sold	0.24136750

There may be scope for further research to further increase the interpretability of our results. One possible approach may entail training a supervised classifier e.g. random forest with $x_{training}=record_norm_features$ and $y=record_cluster$. $feature_importances_can$ yield insight onto the drivers for our results since it gives us the statistical accumulation of the decrease in the impurity within each tree.

Alternatively, the analysis of the distribution for each feature in each cluster may shed some light on how these also affect clustering.

VI. FURTHER RESEARCH

The list below outlines potential further research that was mentioned in this article and that we may enhance once the core methodologies have been completed.

- Enhancement to Entity Resolution with KLSH publication: Replacement of KLSH for Hierarchical clustering
- Enhancement to Entity Resolution with KLSH publication: Adding record name phonetic encoding and its vectorization or one hot encoding to KLSH feature inputs
- Blocking hierarchical order optimization via Bayesian optimization: Instead of banking on a single blocking phonetic rule to block, we add additional blocking rules (e.g. numeric bins, etc) to generate a graph. We run Bayesian optimization to select the hierarchical

order of rules, alter rule values (e.g. number of bins, sampling such as $np.linspace$, $np.logspace$, etc).

- Application of multiple similarity methods as an ensemble: Application of different pre-processing methods to run similarity measures including cosine similarity and dot product to capture both angle and magnitude.
- Normalization of the transformed features as input to the K-Means algorithm and thereby remove the influence of magnitude, unlike the K-Means Euclidean distance. A more laborious but perhaps insightful approach may be by filtering out input records for the K-Means algorithm based on cosine similarity to focus on the angle between vectors.
- Unsupervised k-determination classifier: Train a classifier such as XGBoost, and using $X_{training_dataset}$ composed of the record features, Elbow KneeLocator K result, silhouette score K result, and a desired F-1/Precision/Recall target; the $Y_{training_dataset}$ the ground truth K.
- KLSH Interpretability - Supervised Learning: Train a supervised classifier e.g. random forest with $x_{training}=record_norm_features$ and $y=record_cluster$. $feature_importances_can$ yield insight onto the drivers for our results since it gives us the statistical accumulation of the impurity decrease within each tree.
- KLSH Interpretability: A violin plot can shed light on the distribution for each feature in each cluster and thus the importance each feature plays on the final clustering classification.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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TECH STACK

- Language: Python
- Key Libraries: Pytorch, Sklearn, Torchmetrics, Matplotlib
- Tested on Windows 11 system, 64GB RAM, GPU NVIDIA GeForce RTX 5080 16GB, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 32GB, CPU 12th Gen Intel i9-12900K, 3400Mhz, 16 cores.